

European Union

This project has received funding
from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101003673

I-MOVE-COVID-19 Network

**Multidisciplinary European network for research, prevention and control of
the COVID-19 pandemic**

COVID-19 European primary care surveillance: D2.7 Third Surveillance Bulletin

Author(s)	Nivel and Epiconcept
WP number	2
Title	D2.7 Third Surveillance Bulletin
Date	15 March 2022
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6339931

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Version history

Version	Date finalised	Created/modified by	Comments
v1	23/02/2022	Nivel	Draft version circulated among partners
Final	14/03/2022	Nivel	Final version

Abbreviations

ARI	Acute respiratory infection
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
EEA	European Economic Area
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EU	European Union
GP	General Practitioner
ILI	Influenza-like illness
I-MOVE	Influenza – Monitoring Vaccine Effectiveness in Europe
RCGP RSC	Royal College of General Practitioners Research and Surveillance Centre
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome – coronavirus 2
VE	Vaccine effectiveness

1. Summary

1.1. Background

This surveillance report summarises the information from the nine I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance networks to monitor the COVID-19 pandemic in seven European countries. The I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance in primary care aims to reinforce and complement the COVID-19 epidemiological data in the EU/EEA and the UK, compiled and reported by ECDC. Throughout this surveillance report, persons who tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 virus in primary care are referred to as “COVID-19 cases”.

This third formal surveillance bulletin describes the period from July until December 2021 in detail, and more concisely shows a comparison between previous reporting periods on a number of case characteristics. The previous formal surveillance bulletins encompassed: 1.) March – July 2020 (released Sept 2020, D2.5) and 2.) March 2020 – January 2021 (released March 2021, D2.6). Additionally to the formal deliverables, two interim surveillance bulletins were released: a.) encompassing January – April 2021 (released July 2021) and b.) encompassing May – August 2021 (released December 2021).

Data for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance in primary care is collected following a generic protocol that was adapted by sites to their specific context. To account for study site differences, for instance due to differences in health care systems or coding of data, data was pooled using random effects logistic regression. Seven out of nine sites provided information on sequencing of viruses found in SARS-CoV-2 positive patients.

1.2. Key findings

July to December 2021

- All participating study sites provided data for COVID-19 surveillance in primary care.
- A total of 48,783 COVID-19 cases were reported by nine participating networks in the period July 2021 – December 2021.
- Some peculiarities have to be taken into account in interpreting the data:
 - The Spanish region of Navarra reported the majority of cases, due to their sampling method.
 - Sweden closed their sentinel surveillance between week 20 and week 40.
 - The majority of COVID-19 cases was diagnosed by a rapid antigen test (77%), the other cases were confirmed by a PCR-test (23%). The large number of cases diagnosed by a rapid antigen test was influenced by Navarra (82% cases received a rapid antigen test). In Ireland and Scotland all cases were confirmed by a PCR-test, in France 66%, Portugal 87%, and in Spain 54% of cases received a PCR-test. For England, the Netherlands, and Sweden information regarding the test type was not available.
- The majority of cases were reported in the age band 25 to 49 years (40%). For females almost 42%, for males more than 38% of cases fell within this age band.

- The most frequently reported symptoms were cough (72%) and fever (56%). The least often reported symptom was vomiting (7%).
- Within age groups, percentages of reported symptoms varied. For instance, whereas cough was reported for 63% of cases in the age band 0 – 24 years, in the age group 65 – 79 years for far more cases (81%) cough was reported.
- The median time between onset of symptoms and date of testing was 2 days (IQR 1-4).
- Any chronic condition was reported for 45% of the cases of 25 years and older, with the majority of cases in the oldest age groups reporting any condition: 57% among cases of 65 – 79 years and 70% among cases of 80 years and older. The most often reported chronic condition was heart disease among the age group of 80 years and older (47%), followed by diabetes among age group 80 years and older (24%).
- Chronic conditions were more often reported for males compared with females: for any chronic condition 43% for males versus 38% for females. Heart disease was reported for 11% of the males versus 7% of the females, diabetes for 7% of males and 5% of the females.
- The majority of COVID-19 cases of 15 years and older never smoked (67%), 10% formerly smoked and almost 19% of the cases currently smoked.
- Seasonal influenza vaccination 2020-2021 was reported for 13% of COVID-19 cases aged 25 years and older (n=6,397). Among the age group (65 years and older) with an indication for vaccination, the vaccination rate was higher. For females of 65 to 79 years 46%, versus 48% for males. For females of 80 years and older 69% versus 64% for males.
- COVID-19 vaccination rates among COVID-19 cases aged 25 years and older were higher in the older age groups, with highest proportion in the ≥ 80 years old (90% for females, 87% for males). Among the other age groups vaccination rates did not differ between females and males. Within the age-bands 65-79 and 50-64 years 70-71%, and 48% in the age-band of 25 to 49 years, received at least one vaccination of any vaccine product. This vaccine coverage is overall at time of swab, when the patient was not necessarily part of the target group for vaccination in their country.
- A selection of specimens from COVID-19 positive patients from seven sites was used for virus isolation and sequencing of viruses (n=752). The dominant lineage from July to December was B.1.617.2 (including all sub-lineages, Delta), in December B.1.1.529 (including sub-lineages, Omicron) started to emerge (26% of sequenced cases).

March 2020 to December 2021

- In the period March 2020 to December 2021, the nine study sites reported a total of 91,120 COVID-19 cases.
- The vast majority of cases was reported in December 2021 (38%).
- In the early phase of the pandemic (March-June 2020), higher proportions of cases in older age-bands were observed, whereas a shift to younger age-bands was observed in subsequent reporting periods. In May to August 2021 there was a surge in cases within the age-band 15-24 years (more than 23% in both females and males).
- Throughout March 2020 to December 2021, cough was the most often reported symptom in COVID-19 cases. Anosmia/ageusia was reported for lower proportions of cases as the pandemic emerged (31% in March-June 2020 versus 12% in July-December 2021), whereas coryza was

observed in higher proportions of cases (30% in March-June 2020 versus 43% in July-December 2021).

- At least 41% of cases of 25 years and older was reported to have any chronic condition.
- A selection of specimens from COVID-19 cases from eight sites was used for virus isolation and sequencing of viruses (n=1,824). From January 2021, the B.1.1.7 (Alpha) lineage emerged and became dominant from March to June 2021. In June B.1.617.2 (Delta) was first observed and became the dominant variant from July 2021 onwards.

2. Enhanced COVID-19 surveillance

2.1. Description of participating networks

Table 1 briefly describes participating networks and their contribution of data to this report. Note that the time period for which data were submitted does not necessarily reflect the total duration of the data collection, nor the epidemic in that country. In many countries, dedicated COVID-19 testing hubs were established in 2020, impacting on the data collection for virological surveillance carried out by sentinel GPs prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In some countries, new sentinel GP data collection systems were established.

Table 1. Description of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance networks, July 2021 to December 2021

Network (country)	Participating Institutes	Coverage or number of participating GP practices
RCGP RSC (England), SARS CoV-2 swab testing was performed in the Respiratory Virus Unit, UKHSA Colindale and at dedicated COVID-19 community testing centres	Department of Health (DH); University of Oxford (UOXF);	134 practices*
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	Sorbonne Université (SU); Institut Pasteur (IP)	~ 600 practices
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	Health Service Executive (HSE)	60
Navarra (Spain)	Organismo Autonomo Instituto de Salud Publica Y Laboral de Navarra	53
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands), virological testing of the samples is performed at the RIVM	Nivel (Netherlands Instituut voor Onderzoek van de Gezondheidszorg); Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM)	~ 40 practices
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	Instituto Nacional de Saude dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA)	13 COVID-19 centres for medical consultation and testing of ARI patients
NHS community pathways, primarily comprising COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	NHS National Services Scotland (NHSNS)	~ 14 NHS Boards across Scotland
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII); Ministerio da Saude – Republica Portuguesa (MS)	53 GPs and 27 paediatricians in three regions
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	Folkhälsomyndigheten (FOHM)	~ 37 practices

* From January 2021 onwards only the sentinel virological surveillance information for England was included.

England (EN) – Data is collected from the sentinel GP practices participating in the RCGP RSC network. For surveillance purposes, data were selected from patients with symptoms consulting their GP with a diagnosis of "COVID-19", "COVID-19 illness" or "Main symptom" (i.e. presenting with fever, cough, loss of sense of smell, or loss of sense of taste) and tested for positive for SARS-CoV-2. We excluded records of subsequent positive SARS-CoV-2 tests.

France (FR) – Data is collected from all ARI patients consulting in primary care with GPs participating in the Sentinelles network. Since week 21 2020, the national testing strategy implemented by public health authorities recommended that all patients consulting in primary care with COVID-19 symptoms should be referred to a medical lab for SARS-CoV-2 testing. Thus, since then, the routine Sentinelles data collection has been adapted, with Sentinel general practitioners reporting more information on symptoms and comorbidities, as well as the results of SARS-CoV-2 diagnostic tests (RT-PCR or antigen test, conducted in medical laboratories, or during the GP consultation). Information on other respiratory viruses is not collected.

Ireland (IE) – At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, virological surveillance with the Irish sentinel GP network was disrupted, when face to face GP consultations were stopped. All patients with COVID-19 like symptoms are advised to phone their GP. Virological surveillance with the sentinel GP network was re-established in November 2020, including all COVID-19 phone consultations to the sentinel GP network. Surveillance of COVID-19 with the Irish sentinel GP network was integrated into the national COVID-19 referral pathway, with all patents with COVID-19 symptoms referred to COVID-19 community testing centres for swabbing. Sentinel GP specimens are identified and routed directly to the National Virus Reference Laboratory for SARS-CoV-2 testing. Data reported includes all patients meeting the Irish COVID-19 case definition and consulting (via phone) a sentinel GP in Ireland. Sentinel GP patients without COVID-19 symptoms were excluded.

Navarra (NA) – The data is collected from ARI patients in primary care from all the Navarra population. Since week 20 in 2020, all outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms have been tested. From all outpatients, information on demographic characteristics, major chronic conditions, influenza and COVID-19 vaccination status, variant and sequencing of viruses was collected. Patients with prior SARS-CoV-2 infection were excluded.

Netherlands (NL) – The routine influenza surveillance system in sentinel primary care practices was continued, with additional testing for SARS-CoV-2 of all samples in addition to influenza and other respiratory viruses. From 1 June 2020, every citizen with any respiratory symptom can request a diagnostic (PCR) test at dedicated testing centres. Therefore the number of ILI/ARI patients in primary care eligible for swabbing has decreased considerably and is not representative for all persons suspected of COVID-19.

Portugal (PT) – A new sentinel surveillance system was set up, based on a selection of ARI cases among patients visiting primary care centres with respiratory symptoms. Cases were selected using a systematic sampling method (five cases/week per centre). Laboratory data for SARS-CoV-2 and influenza were available for all cases. Information on underlying chronic diseases and medication are available through data linkage.

Scotland (SC) - The routine GP Sentinel Swabbing Scheme for influenza was stepped down as consultations stopped at practice level. Instead, dedicated NHS COVID-19 triage hubs and community assessment centres were set up across Scotland. From June 2020, patients who are unwell in the community with symptoms compatible with COVID-19 are referred for NHS clinical assessment, either in person or over the telephone. These patients are offered a diagnostic COVID-19 test and asked to provide information about themselves to Public Health Scotland (self-reported by the patient or supplied by the clinical assessment centre) for COVID-19 surveillance purposes. Those patients for whom a test result and enhanced surveillance data are available are included in the community surveillance dataset.

Spain (ES) – The well-consolidated Spanish Influenza Sentinel Surveillance System in primary care was disrupted with the emergence of COVID-19 pandemic, just when the influenza season 2019-20 was almost finishing in Spain. Because of surveillance work since June 2020, a new Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections in Primary Care has been implemented in Spain. For the purpose of this report, data from three Spanish regions are included, although other regions are already working and will become participant in a near future. Data from all ARI cases consulting sentinel primary care are collected with information on sex, age, symptoms and presumption of ILI. Respiratory swabs are systematically taken from the first two-five ARI patients per week. From those swabbed patients, information on chronic diseases, virological and influenza and COVID-19 vaccination is collected. Improving completeness of variables is ongoing.

Sweden (SE) – Data and samples for both enhanced and aggregated surveillance are collected on all patients with influenza-like illness (ILI) and acute respiratory infection (ARI) who consult a sentinel physician. The existing influenza sentinel surveillance system was expanded in week 10 of 2020 to include COVID-19. While the influenza sentinel surveillance phased out in week 16 of 2020, the COVID-19 sentinel surveillance remained active throughout 2020. During the first wave in 2020, sentinel practices had exclusive access to COVID-19 testing for health workers and those with moderate or severe illness. This led to increased numbers attending for consultation with a three-fold increase in sentinel samples taken. Generalised access to testing from June 2020 led to major declines in participating practices. Efforts are now ongoing to encourage GPs to participate given access to both influenza and COVID-19 testing and financial reimbursement for the first five swabs taken per week. In 2021 the sentinel surveillance returned to the seasonal design and paused between week 20 and week 40.

Table 2. Main characteristics of I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance systems, July 2021 to December 2021

Network (country)	Case definition*	Testing strategy
RCGP RSC (England)	ILI or ARI	Sentinel testing
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	ARI	All patients
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	ARI or ILI**	All patients meeting the COVID-19 case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2. All patients meeting the influenza case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2 and influenza.
Navarra (Spain)	ARI	All outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample
Rede Médicos-Sentinel (Portugal)	ARI	All patients, but a systematic sample is provided for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	ILI or ARI or altered sense of smell/taste	All patients are tested, but only those for whom enhanced surveillance data are also available are included in the community surveillance programme.
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	ARI	Systematic sample
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample

* ILI = influenza-like illness; ARI = acute respiratory illness

** Irish case definitions: www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/coronavirus/novelcoronavirus/casedefinitions/covid-19interimcasedefinitionforireland/ (COVID-19) and www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/influenza/casedefinitions/ (influenza)

Table 3. Site-specific surveillance websites of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 networks, July 2021 to December 2021

Network (country)	URL
RCGP RSC (England)	www.rcgp.org.uk/rsc
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	https://www.sentiweb.fr/france/en/?page=bulletin
Irish sentinel GP network (Ireland)	www.hpsc.ie
Navarra (Spain)	http://www.navarra.es/home_es/Gobierno+de+Navarra/Organigrama/Los+departamentos/Salud/Organigrama/Estructura+Organica/Instituto+Navarro+de+Salud+Publica/Publicaciones/Publicaciones+profesionales/Epidemiologia/InformesVigilanciaEpidemiologia2021.htm
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	www.nivel.nl/nl/nivel-zorgregistraties-eerste-lijn/actuele-weekcijfers-aandoeningen-waaronder-griep-surveillance https://www.rivm.nl/griep-grieprik/feiten-en-cijfers
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	www.insa.min-saude.pt/category/informacao-e-cultura-cientifica/publicacoes/atividade-gripal/
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	www.hps.scot.nhs.uk/web-resources-container/enhanced-surveillance-of-covid-19-in-scotland-community-surveillance-protocol/
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	vgripe.isciii.es/inicio.do www.isciii.es/QueHacemos/Servicios/VigilanciaSaludPublicaRENAVE/EnfermedadesTransmisibles/Paginas/Gripe.aspx
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/smittskydd-beredskap/overvakning-och-rapportering/sentinelovervakning/

NOTE:

All figures in this report are based on data reported by I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care networks from July 2021 to December 2021, apart from paragraph 2.17 and 2.18. These include data reported from the start of the project in March 2020 to the final data extract for surveillance including December 2021.

The results reported are approved by all partners.

Data have been weighted for differences between study sites, due to sample size and data collection methods, using random effects logistic models with study site as random effect. Total percentages may therefore not add up to 100%.

In this report, COVID-19 cases are laboratory confirmed for SARS-CoV-2 or diagnosed by rapid antigen tests.

2.2. Data on COVID-19 cases

Figure 1 depicts the number of COVID-19 cases, selected for testing in the primary care surveillance networks and with a positive test result for SARS-CoV-2. Please note that the y-axis is different between networks. In total, the study sites reported 48,783 COVID-19 cases during the period July – December 2021.

Figure 1. Number of COVID-19 cases reported by I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care networks by week*, July 2021 to December 2021

* Week number refers to the week in which the swab specimen was taken. Week numbers range from week 26 to week 52 in 2021.

2.3. Demographic characteristics of COVID-19 cases

The age profile of COVID-19 cases presenting to primary care may be younger as they are generally milder cases compared to hospitalised patients. Older, more severe cases may not be fully represented in this dataset. In Portugal, for example, being 65 years or older is one of the criteria to be referred to a hospital emergency department. In several countries, among others Ireland and the Netherlands, the primary care surveillance systems exclude residents of long term care facilities.

Figure 2. Percentage of COVID-19 cases by age group, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=48,783)

Figure 3. Percentage of COVID-19 cases, distribution of age groups by sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=48,766)

2.4. Symptoms of COVID-19 cases

Results on symptoms are based on data reported by different countries for each symptom, and are reported only if collected in at least two countries. The reporting of symptoms may be related to the definition of patients eligible for I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance by protocol. Therefore, asymptomatic cases are not expected.

Figure 4. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n*)

* n in pooled data differs according to symptom (n in pooled data, countries): cough: n=4,359 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fever: n=4,322 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: n=2,778 (FR, PT, SC), coryza: n=1,118 (FR, NL, PT), headache: n=4,340 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), sore throat: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), myalgia: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), anosmia-ageusia: n=4,304 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC, SE), shortness of breath: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), diarrhoea: n=4,005 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC, SE**), vomiting: n=3,989 (ES, FR, PT, SC, SE**). ** SE collects 'vomiting or diarrhoea'.

Figure 5. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases by age-group, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n*)

* n in pooled data differs according to symptom (n in pooled data, countries): cough: n=4,359 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fever: n=4,322 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: n=2,778 (FR, PT, SC), coryza: n=1,118 (FR, NL, PT), headache: n=4,340 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), sore throat: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), myalgia: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), anosmia-ageusia: n=4,304 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC, SE), shortness of breath: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), diarrhoea: n=4,005 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC, SE**), vomiting: n=3,989 (ES, FR, PT, SC, SE**). ** SE collects 'vomiting or diarrhoea'.

Figure 6. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases, by sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n*)

A.

B.

* n in pooled data differs according to symptom (n in pooled data, countries): cough: n=4,359 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fever: n=4,322 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: n=2,778 (FR, PT, SC), coryza: n=1,118 (FR, NL, PT), headache: n=4,340 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), sore throat: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), myalgia: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), anosmia-ageusia: n=4,304 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC, SE), shortness of breath: n=4,331 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,682 (ES, FR, IE, NL, PT), diarrhoea: n=4,005 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC, SE**), vomiting: n=3,989 (ES, FR, PT, SC, SE**). **SE collects 'vomiting or diarrhoea'.

2.5. Time between onset of symptoms and testing

The median time between onset of symptoms and date of testing was 2 days (IQR 1-4). The median time between onset and testing was constant over July to December 2021.

Table 4. Number of days between onset of symptoms and swab specimen was taken, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data n=4,435)

	Number of cases	Median	25 th Percentile	75 th Percentile
All COVID-19 cases	4,435	2	1	4
By month (2021)				
July	799	2	1	4
August	753	2	1	4
September	501	2	1	4
October	335	2	1	4
November	705	2	1	4
December	1,342	2	1	3
By age group				
0 – 4 yrs	199	2	1	3
5 – 14 yrs	419	2	1	3
15 – 24 yrs	633	2	1	3
25 – 49 yrs	1,806	2	1	4
50 – 64 yrs	894	2	1	4
65 – 79 yrs	377	3	2	5
80+ yrs	107	2	1	4
By sex				
Female	2,545	2	1	3
Male	1,875	2	1	4

2.6. Co-infections of COVID-19 cases

Data on co-infections with influenza were provided by Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Scotland, Spain, and Sweden. One co-infection with influenza virus was reported by Spain, in the age-band 25-49 years in week 51. Data on co-infections with respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), rhinovirus, seasonal coronavirus, and human metapneumo virus (HMPV) were provided by Ireland, the Netherlands, and Scotland. Seasonal coronavirus was observed in 11 COVID-19 cases, of whom four in the age-band 0-4 years (week 47 and 52 in Scotland, week 47 in Ireland, and week 50 in the Netherlands), two in the age-band 15-24 years (week 47 in Ireland, week 52 in Scotland), four persons in the age-band 25-49 years (week 46, 50, and 51 in Scotland, week 52 in Ireland), and one person in the age-band 50-64 years (week 49 in Scotland). RSV was observed in three COVID-19 cases, of whom two in Scotland, in the age-band 0-4 years in week 44 and in the age-band 50-64 years in week 52, and one person in Ireland in the age-band 24-49 years in week 48. Rhinovirus was observed in nine COVID-19 cases, of whom three in the age-band 65-79 years (week 49, 51, and 52 in Scotland), two in the age-band 15-24 years (week 49 and 50 in Scotland), two in the age-band 0-4 years (both week 50, in the Netherlands and Scotland), and two persons in the age-band 25-49 years (week 50 in Scotland, week 52 in Ireland). HMPV was observed in three COVID-19 cases in Scotland, of whom one in the age-band 0-4 years (week 48) and two in the age-band 25-49 years (week 48, 50).

Ireland and Scotland provided data on co-infections with adenovirus, which was observed in three COVID-19 cases in the age-band 0-4 years (week 47, 51 in Scotland) and one in the age-band 15-24 years (week 47 in Ireland). Ireland and the Netherlands provided data on co-infection with parainfluenza virus, which was observed in one COVID-19 case in Ireland in the age-band 0-4 years (week 44). Ireland provided data on co-infections with bocavirus, which was observed in five COVID-19 cases, of whom one in the age-band 0-4 years (week 52), one in the age-band 5-14 years (week 52), one in the age-band 25-49 years (week 52), and two persons in the age-band 50-64 years (week 45). No co-infections with enterovirus were detected (only provided by the Netherlands).

2.7. Referral to hospital of COVID-19 cases

Data regarding referral to hospital was provided by France and Spain. 60 COVID-19 cases were referred (3%), of whom 19 (32%) in the age band 25 to 49 years, 9 (15%) persons in the age-band 50-64 years, 13 persons (22%) in the age-band 65-79 years, and 16 persons (27%) of 80 years and older.

2.8. Underlying (chronic) conditions of COVID-19 cases

Results on underlying chronic conditions are based on data reported by all countries, except for Scotland on individual chronic conditions. Exceptions are cancer and asthma, that were not collected by all countries (cancer was not collected in England, the Netherland, and Spain; asthma was not collected in Ireland and the Netherlands, in Spain asthma was included as ‘lung disease’). In Scotland, data collection regarding individual chronic conditions has been stopped until week 43 and started again from week 44 onwards. Until week 43, instead people were asked ‘Did you receive a letter asking you to shield’, which was sent to those with a serious chronic condition and people who were pregnant or obese. This was included in the variable ‘any chronic condition’ only.

Figure 7. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data n=32,782*, cancer: n=31,636, asthma: n=31,029)

* Based on the variable ‘presence of any chronic condition’ for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

Figure 8. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases, by age group, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data n=48,782*, cancer: n=46,231, asthma: n=45,764)

* Based on the variable 'presence of any chronic condition' for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

Figure 9. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older, by sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data n=32,782*, cancer: n=31,636, asthma: n=31,029)

* Based on the variable 'presence of any chronic condition' for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

2.9. Obesity among COVID-19 cases

Information on obesity was collected in England, France, Ireland, Navarra, the Netherlands, Portugal, Scotland, and Spain. Obese was defined as a Body Mass Index (BMI) of 30 or higher, except for Navarra (BMI of 40 or higher). Obesity was reported for 943 COVID-19 cases (2%), most of whom were female (64%).

2.10. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases

The results on smoking status are presented for cases aged 15 years or older. A former smoker ceased smoking more than one year ago. Smoking status was collected by Navarra, the Netherlands, Scotland, and Spain.

Figure 10. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases aged 15 years or older, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=12,524)

Figure 11. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases aged 15 years or older, by sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=12,524)

2.11. Pregnancy status of COVID-19 cases

Results on pregnancy are restricted to female COVID-19 patients aged between 15 and 49 years. Data regarding pregnancy were provided by France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Scotland, Spain, and Sweden. 68 COVID-19 cases were pregnant (5%).

2.12. Seasonal influenza vaccination status of COVID-19 cases

The result of seasonal influenza vaccination status are based on the data collected by all countries. Seasonal influenza vaccination status refers to being vaccinated in 2020. Results are presented for

cases aged 25 years or older, because immunisation programmes for younger age groups differ between countries.

Figure 12. Received seasonal influenza vaccination, COVID-19 cases aged 25 years or older by age and sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=32,144)

2.13. COVID-19 vaccination rates among COVID-19 cases

The results of COVID-19 vaccination status are based on the data collected by all countries. The onset of vaccination programmes, eligible age-groups, and vaccine products used (i.e. AstraZeneca, Janssen, Moderna, and Pfizer) differed between countries. Vaccination status refers to cases who received at least one dose of any vaccine, for age-groups of 25 years and older. Of all cases of 25 years and older, 86% received at least one vaccination. The overall vaccine coverage (for receiving at least one dose) is mainly influenced by the vaccine coverage of Navarra. Taking country differences into account, the graph below, with the weighted results, reports lower vaccination rates. Please note that in figure 13, vaccine coverage is based on vaccination status at time of swabbing, when the patient was not necessarily part of the target group for vaccination in their country.

Figure 13. Received at least one vaccination for SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 cases aged 25 years or older by age and sex, July 2021 to December 2021 (pooled data, n=32,588)

2.14. Health care workers among COVID-19 cases

Data regarding whether a COVID-19 case was a healthcare worker was provided by Navarra and Scotland. In Navarra and Scotland 874 COVID-19 cases were indicated as healthcare worker (2%).

2.15. Recent travel of COVID-19 cases

Data on recent travel was collected by the Netherlands and Sweden. One case was observed who recently travelled abroad.

2.16. Sequence and isolate viruses of respiratory samples from COVID-19 positive cases

A selection of specimens from COVID-19 positive patients in Ireland, Navarra, the Netherlands, Portugal, Scotland, Spain, and Sweden were used for virus isolation and sequencing of viruses. The sequencing results are shared in GISAID. Dedicated bioinformatics pipelines will be used for analysis of viral sequencing data. These data will be provided to WP4 for epidemiological and modelling studies. According to the WHO labelling of SARS-CoV-2 variants of interest and concern, from July onwards, the Delta variant became dominant, in August the Delta variant surpassed all other variants. Although in December the Delta variant was still dominant, the Omicron variant started to emerge. In figure 14, the emergence of the variants of concern from the start of the pandemic is depicted.

Table 5. Characterised viruses of COVID-19 cases, by country and month, July 2021 to December 2021

	Total N	Lineages				
		B.1.617.2 ^a N (%)	B.1.1.529 ^b N (%)	B.1.1.7 N (%)	B.1.351 N (%)	Other lineages ^c N (%)
Total SARS-CoV-2 sequenced	752	667 (88.7)	45 (6.0)	13 (1.7)	6 (0.8)	21 (3.0)
Month (2021)						
July	122	100 (82.0)	0 (0)	13 (10.7)	5 (4.1)	4 (3.2)
August	106	103 (97.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0.9)	2 (1.9)
September	75	75 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
October	130	125 (96.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (4.5)
November	148	148 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
December	171	116 (67.8)	45 (26.3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	10 (5.8)
Country						
Ireland	71	70 (98.6)	0 (0)	1 (1.4)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Navarra	485	445 (91.8)	9 (1.9)	9 (1.9)	6 (1.2)	16 (3.3)
the Netherlands	6	6 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Portugal	7	7 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Scotland	139	114 (82.0)	25 (18.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Spain	42	23 (54.8)	11 (26.2)	3 (7.1)	0 (0)	5 (11.9)
Sweden	2	2 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

^a Including sub-lineages (in order of frequency and detected > 1) AY.43, AY.4, AY.42, AY.5, AY.36, AY.102, AY.122, AY.124, AY.33, AY.39.1, AY.4.2, AY.98.1, AY.44, AY.94, AY.121, AY.127, AY.34, AY.9.

^b Including sub-lineages BA.1, BA.1.1

^c Other lineages include B.1, B.1.621, C.37, C.37.1, P.1, P.1.17, and not specified

Figure 14. Characterised viruses according to variant of concern of COVID-19 cases, by month, March 2020 to December 2021

* Including sub-lineages

2.17. Epidemiological curve pooled COVID-19 cases, March 2020 to December 2021

For a comprehensive overview of COVID-19 cases reported in primary care surveillance, the pooled data for all study sites from week 8 in March 2020 to week 52 in December 2021 are depicted in figure 14. During the period March 2020 to December 2021, a total number of 91,120 COVID-19 cases was reported by the nine study sites.

Figure 15. Number of COVID-19 cases from start of surveillance in March (week 8) 2020 to December (week 52) 2021

2.18. Characteristics of pooled COVID-19 cases, compared for different periods during the pandemic, March 2020 to December 2021

For an indication how main patient characteristics of pooled COVID-19 positive cases evolved during the pandemic, graphs from previous bulletins are compiled in figure 16 to 18.

Please note that data collection differed between the reporting periods, and in the early phase of the pandemic not all countries were able to deliver data.

During the first months of the pandemic (March-June 2020), much more cases were reported in the age-band 50-79 years, particularly among females. During the whole period, most cases were observed in the age-band 25-49 years, both in females and males. Over the course of the pandemic, the number of cases in the oldest age-band diminished, whereas the number of cases in the younger age-bands (0-24 years) increased. In May to August 2021, there was a surge in cases in the age-band 15-24 years.

Figure 16. Percentage of COVID-19 cases, distribution of age groups by sex (pooled data)

During the first pandemic period, higher proportions of symptoms were reported in COVID-19 cases than subsequent periods. Particularly fatigue and shortness of breath were observed in relatively more cases between March and June 2020. Cough and fever were observed in a majority of cases throughout the whole reporting period.

Figure 17. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases (pooled data)*

* Pooled data differs according to symptom

For a large minority of COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older, during the whole reporting period any chronic condition was reported. The most often reported chronic condition was heart disease, percentages varied over time.

Figure 18. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older (pooled data)

* Pooled data differs according to underlying condition, based on the variable 'presence of any chronic condition' for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

3. Background

The end of 2019 saw the emergence of a novel severe acute respiratory syndrome – coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which causes coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium aims to obtain epidemiological and clinical information on patients with COVID-19 as well as virological information on SARS-CoV-2, through different work packages (WP):

- a) provision of a flexible surveillance platform, adaptable to the epidemiological situation, through WP2 (primary care surveillance) and WP3 (hospital surveillance)
- b) research studies, through WP4, and
- c) evaluation of public health interventions (e.g. vaccination, antivirals) in WP2–4

in order to contribute to the knowledge base, guide patient management, and inform the public health response. This is being achieved through adaptation and expansion of the existing I-MOVE network to include COVID-19. The network includes primary care networks, hospitals, and national laboratory reference centres in 10 countries across the WHO European Region.¹

The WP2 primary care surveillance for COVID-19 is coordinated by Nivel (Netherlands institute for health services research). The I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care network comprises nine sentinel surveillance networks in six European Union (EU) Member States (MS)² and in England and Scotland. The laboratory component of the network includes regional and national reference centres from the participating countries. While each of the surveillance sites analyses their data separately, pooling the data for overall analysis will provide a sample size big enough to answer study questions with reasonable precision.

The I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium, coordinated by Epiconcept, was created following the European Commission's Call for Proposals H2020 "Advancing Knowledge for the Clinical and Public Health Response to the Emerging Coronavirus Epidemic". It brings together many partners already involved in the [I-MOVE](#) (Influenza - Monitoring Vaccine Effectiveness in Europe) network. I-MOVE, first established in 2007, was the first network to monitor influenza vaccine effectiveness (VE) within and across the seasons in the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA). The network has two components, one for primary care practices, recruiting patients with influenza-like illness (ILI) and the other for hospitals, recruiting patients with severe acute respiratory illness (SARI). In February 2020, I-MOVE partners came together as the I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium, and were successful in a bid for the H2020 call on "Advancing knowledge for the clinical and public health response to the novel coronavirus epidemic".

In this third formal surveillance report of COVID-19 in primary care, results are presented from participating primary care COVID-19 surveillance networks from July to December 2021. The results add to the ECDC surveillance data collection through TESSy (NCOVAGGR) and reporting (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/surveillance/weekly-surveillance-report>) by providing more detailed information of COVID-19 cases in primary care.

¹ Albania, France, Lithuania, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and the UK (England and Scotland).

² France, Ireland, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain (two sites: the Spanish national system and the Navarra regional system) and Sweden.

More details on the data collection for I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance can be found in the Generic Protocol.³ Briefly, the I-MOVE network is nested in sentinel practices carrying out surveillance for influenza and now COVID-19. Data is being collected from community-dwelling individuals who consult a participating physician with symptoms of suspected COVID-19. From all or from a systematic sample of suspected COVID-19 cases, primary care practitioners collect respiratory specimens as well as information on patient characteristics, and if possible, also on symptoms and potential risk factors and preventive factors for COVID-19. We refer to lab-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 COVID-19 patients as ‘COVID-19 cases’. Participating primary care networks have implemented the generic protocol in their surveillance setting.

³ <https://www.imoveflu.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D2.3-I-MOVE-COVID-19-Phased-surveillance-protocol.pdf>